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Editing Purcell's keyboard music: some reflections on collected editions, past and future

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ABSTRACT

The authors examine the challenges of editing Purcell's keyboard music in the context of their completion of a printed volume for the Purcell Society begun by Christopher Hogwood, and their involvement in 'Digital Directions for Collected Editions', which investigated critical editing of music in the digital domain. Hogwood advocated an inclusive approach that included independent arrangements by various scribes of the same material. The printed volume will arrange items by key; a digital edition would allow flexibility to order pieces in other ways. As recent research shows, variance between sources often reflects aspects of performance practice that can be applied more broadly to keyboard music of the period, as well as revision by the composer; this has implications for how variance should be treated in critical editions. The authors consider the challenges of presentation within the confines of a printed volume and suggest the potential of digital editions for addressing them, arguing for use of *ossias* in the former and flexibility of presentation in the latter. A digital edition allows a multidimensional approach where primary sources can serve as a base text corrected by reference to other versions that can be displayed to give the user a sense of other possibilities. In terms of any future digital edition of Purcell's keyboard music, questions surrounding financial sustainability, data preservation and software maintenance will rely on the development of user communities: user interfaces will need to meet the needs of a young pianist as well as those of a specialist in early music.

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1. Introduction

The lure of technology can result in the pursuit of the digital for its own sake rather than to meet a need. This article represents an attempt to identify issues specific to the editing of Purcell's keyboard music in relation to past editions, an edition being prepared by the authors for the print medium, and to a putative future edition in the digital domain. During the course of the article, the opportunities afforded by a digital platform to address such challenges will be identified. However, digital editions are by no means a panacea, and the article ends by tying together these strands in relation to questions surrounding users of such editions and sustainability, both financial and in terms of preservation of data and maintenance of software, which were addressed during an AHRC-funded networking project, 'Digital directions for collected editions: keyboard music by British musicians before c.1700' ('Digital Directions').

A monumental edition comprising the collected keyboard works of a composer such as Henry Purcell

(1659–1695) faces a number of challenges. They include problems such as deciding what should be included and how to interpret sources of varying quality that sometimes present the music in radically different forms. Although there are about four sources with a strong connection to the composer,¹ including an autograph manuscript (*GB-Lbl*, MS Mus. 1),² much of the keyboard music associated with Purcell's name, which includes many arrangements of his music originally for other performing forces, survives in manuscripts written with varying degrees of care and competence by a wide range of musicians. Perhaps, then, it is no surprise that Purcell's keyboard music, volume 6 of the Purcell Society's complete edition (Purcell, 1878–1919) has been one of the last to be revised since it first appeared in 1895. Christopher Hogwood had made significant progress on editing the volume before his untimely death in 2014; since then, work on the volume has been continued by present authors (Hogwood et al., *forthcoming*).

In a valuable essay from 2003 that charted the history of publications of Purcell's keyboard music from

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¹*GB-Lbl*, MS Mus. 1, *GB-Och*, Mus. 1177/1176, *A Choice Collection of Lessons* (London, 1696) and Playford (1689).

²RISM *sigla* are used for libraries throughout this article; see RISM (n.d.).

the early nineteenth century onwards, Hogwood outlined his vision for an ‘inclusive’ volume that aimed to incorporate almost all the keyboard music associated with Purcell’s name in seventeenth- and early-eighteenth-century sources. He also advocated for an edition that provides the user with all the ‘versions’ of pieces that may exist in the sources, arguing that players should be given the opportunity to experiment with each successive instantiation in what he would later call a ‘process edition’ (Hogwood, 2013). In some ways, these views anticipated more recent work on how Restoration musicians generally interacted creatively with music (such as Herissonne, 2013a, especially chapter 6) that draws attention away from a composer-centric view of music towards the study of scribes, manuscripts and their users. However, as we shall see, this same literature has caused us to review some of Hogwood’s editorial decisions, in particular the extent to which variant versions should be considered genuinely distinct from one another and how to express the divergences between them in an edited volume.

Even the very notion of a composer-centred edition begins to seem outmoded in the light of the recent research on scribal creativity in seventeenth-century England. There are, nevertheless, several reasons for accepting Hogwood’s inclusive approach as a means to address some of the aspects of collected editions of music by seventeenth-century composers that today seem to be problematic: it lends coherence to a volume of keyboard repertoire from the period and encourages editors to work to the principle of providing a credible version of the music according to present understanding – in so far as this is possible from the state of survival of the sources – independently of the question of whether or not the music can be linked directly to the composer. This monumental edition thus moves away from a narrow focus on a single genre by a particular composer to encompass an approach that accepts all keyboard music based on Purcell’s music as well as freely composed, idiomatic pieces. Indeed, much of the contents as envisaged by Hogwood and the bulk of his editorial decisions will be retained by us, even if in many instances the detailed work of comparing sources had still yet to be accomplished at his death.

Our article is intended to serve as a fresh review of some of the issues of authorship and authenticity that arise in preparing this edition from the coalface, how it will be situated within the context of previous editions of this music, how Hogwood’s editorial approach was influenced by figures such as Howard Ferguson and Thurston Dart, and how our own approach is informed by more recent research. We shall also look ahead to the future of the collected edition by relating what follows to digital possibilities. To do this, we will pay special attention to: (1) variation between independent arrangements of the

same piece; (2) variant versions of pieces that, on closer inspection, relate to different ways of notating aspects of performance practice; and (3) whether there is evidence of more substantive revisions of keyboard pieces by the composer that could justify treating certain versions of the music as distinct from others.

2. Context of the revised edition of Purcell’s keyboard music for the Purcell Society

It is possible to trace the critical editing of music in embryonic form to the late eighteenth century as the works of the ‘great men’ of music started to be gathered together in published complete works. Such collected editions were intended to produce what were deemed to be authoritative texts by adhering closely to source notation and in some cases by borrowing the philological techniques applied in textual criticism. Indeed, these ideas, which gained sway in the nineteenth century and remained largely unchanged in the twentieth century, are reflected in the earliest editions of Purcell’s keyboard music that treated it as a historical artefact. These include Benjamin Goodison’s projected collected edition of Purcell’s works of 1789, which was to include a volume of ‘Lessons, Voluntaries, &c.’ that never came to fruition, John Stafford Smith’s *Musica Antiqua* (1812) as well as the Purcell Society’s volume 6, ‘Harpsichord and Organ Music’, edited by William Barclay Squire and Edward John Hopkins, and published in 1895.³ They were faithful to original sources in a way that reflected the antiquarian goals of their editors and stood in sharp distinction to nineteenth- and early-twentieth-century editions that adapted the music for modern instruments, such those edited for piano by Ernst Pauer in 1879, which were later supplemented by J.A. Fuller-Maitland’s *The Contemporaries of Purcell* of 1921. Criticising Pauer, Squire argued that his heavily edited editions stopped the performer from ‘seeing the wood because of the trees’ (Squire & Hopkins, 1895, i). In contrast, Squire’s aim was ‘to diverge as little as possible from the original text’ (Squire & Hopkins, 1895, i). Thus, lying behind some of the earliest critical editions of Purcell’s keyboard music was an assumption (widely held at the time) that it was possible – especially through faithfully recording information about the sources and making decisions about their relative reliability – to present the composer’s ‘intentions’ from varying source material and that to change the original notation gave a distorted picture.

The immediate context for Hogwood’s revised volume 6 of the Purcell Society edition was the revival of historically informed instruments and performance

³ ‘Harpsichord’ is used in a generic sense throughout this article to include the virginal and spinet.

practices in the second half of the last century to which he was intimately connected. It is unclear precisely when he began working on it, although two figures, Howard Ferguson and Thurston Dart, played an important role in shaping his interest in Restoration keyboard music. Dart made a notable Purcell recording on harpsichord and clavichord released in 1956 and was responsible for inviting Ferguson to produce a new scholarly complete edition, published by Stainer & Bell in 1964, which drew in part on Franklin Zimmerman's recently published catalogue of Purcell's works (Ferguson, 1964–1965, p. 1; Ferguson, 1964a, 1964b; Zimmerman, 1963). Ferguson's interest in Restoration keyboard music continued into the 1970s when he worked in collaboration with Hogwood on an edition for Stainer & Bell of William Croft's harpsichord music that benefitted from John Caldwell's and Barry Cooper's research on sources which was completed in the same decade (Caldwell, 1973; Cooper, 1974; Croft, 1974). Hogwood subsequently produced editions of several key sources: the first book of the *Harpsichord Master* (1697) and Matthew Locke's 1673 anthology, *Melothesia*, both published by Oxford University Press in 1980 and 1987 respectively, and an edition of the 'fitt for the manicorde' manuscript (a source he owned, formerly belonging to Dart, and now *GB-Lbl*, MS Mus. 1852/10) which was published by Edition HH in 2003b.⁴ Working with Hogwood on the revised Purcell Society volume before he died as one of several assistants he employed over the years, Andrew Woolley recalls that he had inherited Ferguson's transcriptions of Purcell's keyboard music, presumably made in connection with the 1964 edition. Not surprisingly, given their earlier collaboration, this suggests Ferguson exerted influence on Hogwood in his methods, and even though Hogwood later came to criticise aspects of Ferguson's approach, in several respects their views were similar.

The desire, since the nineteenth century, to establish a single, authoritative text for each of Purcell's pieces was a goal that still held sway at the time Ferguson's edition was published. It arose partly from the work concept, but was also born of necessity: the physical, printed format of the collected edition meant that limited space allowed for only one text. However, as will be seen, the source situation today presents a more complex tapestry in which it is clear that fixity of text was limited. Each source presents us with music notation where surface detail can convey aspects of performance practice as recorded by its scribe. Furthermore, the importance of the myriad arrangements of Purcell's theatre music for keyboard has come to be fully recognised, not least because he was intimately involved with keyboard playing in the domestic sphere

himself: Henry Playford takes pride in telling us that the 1689 edition of *The Second Part of Musick's Handmaid* was 'carefully Revised and Corrected by the said Mr. Henry Purcell'. In addition, the relatively recent discovery of graded teaching materials used by Purcell (*GB-Lbl*, MS Mus. 1) even more clearly situates his keyboard practice as much in this world of amateur music-making as in that of the professional keyboard player. This suggests that a modern edition should be as accessible to a young amateur keyboard player as to the specialist scholar-performer, and that any future digital edition of the music should be designed in such a way as to facilitate this.

3. An inclusive volume: arrangements and questions of authorship

In his 2003 essay, Hogwood set out some of the principles of his revised edition, notably his vision for an 'inclusive' volume. Whereas Ferguson had taken the decision to omit a number of pieces he found to be inauthentic on stylistic grounds and sought to limit the number of arrangements to those deemed to be competent, Hogwood argued for an 'open doors' policy reflecting more closely the state of the surviving sources. The role of several individuals in creating the corpus of Purcell's 'complete keyboard music' was made evident to Hogwood from two keyboard versions of a hornpipe also known in a four-part version from Purcell's music for *The Fairy Queen* (1692), one of them in the Purcell keyboard autograph discovered in 1993 (*GB-Lbl*, MS Mus. 1), the other in the 'Essex Deane' manuscript (*GB-En*, MS 3343) copied by the organist and composer Philip Hart probably in the late 1690s (Figure 1). Hogwood did not consider (at least in his essay) the relationship with the four-part version and was also unaware that Hart was the scribe of the Deane manuscript, which became known only in 2000 (Shay & Thompson, 2000, p. 287; Woolley, 2008, pp. 63–68), although he concluded that Hart's arrangement shows at the very least that the large contemporary corpus of Purcell arrangements stemmed from or were reworked by several competent individuals besides Purcell himself (Hogwood, 2003a, p. 79).

This example is instructive: the manner in which the right hand is given the melodic line accompanied by two parts in the left hand is typical of arrangements of theatre tunes made by Purcell himself, and those by other scribes whose identities are often unknown. Hart's version features a more active bass part, although like Purcell's, it is derived from the consort version published in *Ayres for the Theatre* (1697). It is usually the approach to the left-hand accompaniment that differs most between independent settings of the same material; even where the tune is relatively stable with only a few minor differences

⁴ For an indication of Dart's influence on Hogwood, see Hogwood (2009).

The musical score is presented in three systems. Each system consists of a main staff (treble clef) and a bass staff (bass clef). The key signature is one flat (B-flat major), and the time signature is 3/4. The score is marked with measure numbers 5, 10, and 15. The piece concludes with a double bar line at the end of the third system.

Figure 1. Opening of 'Hornpipe' from *The Fairy Queen* (Z.629/1b) arranged for keyboard. Main text: *GB-Lbl*, MS Mus. 1 (Purcell autograph); B: *GB-En*, MS 3343 (Philip Hart autograph).

between arrangements, the bass line can be substantively different.

In dealing with questions of authorship in arrangements, Ferguson advocated a pragmatic approach in terms of what to include in his edition:

As I could find no way of separating the authentic from the unauthentic with any degree of certainty, I... decided to include all those arrangements that at least sounded effective on the keyboard... this solution is both subjective and arbitrary; but at least it has the advantage of preserving many delightful pieces... and of excluding others which, it must be confessed, are distinctly tedious. (Ferguson, 1964–1965, pp. 4–5)

However, there is a risk here of a circular argument, since any judgement of style can be made only on the basis of the surviving music, and if some of this is removed on stylistic grounds then any conclusions will inevitably be flawed. There is a need to consider the audience for which the music was intended, and how this may have affected what we perceive as ‘good’ style. For example, Purcell was clearly engaged with teaching, so any arrangement of his may have been made to meet the needs of an individual pupil. There are also implications relating to potential users of a critical edition in the twenty-first century: a simple, ‘tedious’ arrangement for a seventeenth-century student may have value for a young learner today. It may, nevertheless, become possible to address questions of authorship in the future; one advantage of a digital edition in which all source-texts are encoded is the potential for using computational techniques to investigate authorship.

Where a particular source preserves a unique setting of music by Purcell, it is likely to be an arrangement by a music teacher working in a domestic setting and copying the music for an individual pupil; such pieces do not tend to travel all that far. This is probably the case also for the composer’s own arrangements preserved in *GB-Lbl*, MS Mus. 1, an autograph manuscript. Although some of these are accurately transmitted in other sources, these date from sometime later which suggests that a manuscript stemming from Purcell was available to eighteenth-century copyists. For example, an arrangement of a minuet from *The Double Dealer* (d7; Z.592/7) is found also in *GB-Cfm*, Music MS 653, which was copied c.1715 by the organist and Croft student, James Kent (1700–1774; see Herissone, 2013b). Similarly, Hart’s arrangement mentioned above follows some of the left-hand writing of Purcell’s keyboard autograph quite closely, which suggests he was influenced by an existing keyboard arrangement (Herissone, 2013a, pp. 346–349). Thus, the source situation in arrangements quite frequently reflects a complex web of interrelationships whereby the music takes on forms influenced not by

one but several sources, probably in part due to the role of memory in the transmission of music in the Restoration period. A digital edition that entails the separate encoding of the music as it occurs in each source has the potential to illustrate degrees of relationship between sources, and thus shed light on questions surrounding source relationships, scribes and authorship. By shifting focus from the ‘great composer’ to the activity of scribes and those who used their manuscripts it would be possible to detect traits connecting an individual with several arrangements, even if it is impossible to identify them.

Figure 2 illustrates the immense variety between independent settings of the same air, none of which is likely to be the composer’s own work. As is usual, the right hand has the melodic line, but this differs greatly between the sources. The version on folios 60v–61 of source A illustrates the sort of embellishment that would be stylistically appropriate in a repeated section. Source B is notable for the way slides from a third below the main note have been written out in full rather than using an ornament sign. No two sources agree on how the right-hand tune should sound in terms of surface detail. The left-hand has the usual two-voice texture, but here there is little connection between the arrangements. Each is independent of the others, and there is no reason to think that they left the ambit of the domestic context for which they were written: indeed, the extensive fingering and inclusion of note names in source C illustrates well the circumstances in which such arrangements were made.

Hogwood differed from Ferguson by not excluding pieces on the grounds of incompetence or apparent incompatibility with Purcell’s style, including the Suite in B flat (Z.664), which contains a number of harmonic eccentricities. He argued that dubious pieces should also be included in an edition on the grounds that modern judgements are fallible, and to reflect contemporary understandings of authorship. He also pointed out that music by other composers needed to be included in order to retain some groupings of mixed authorship in the sources, including Purcell’s autograph in which movements from the A minor suite Z. 663 are followed by a Jig that source evidence suggests is probably by John Blow (Woolley, 2018, pp. xvi and 177). The fact that many sources of arrangements have come to light since the 1960s means that the dimensions of the revised Purcell Society edition are unprecedented; Hogwood planned to publish approximately 180 pieces including a large number of variant versions.

The most pressing issue for an edition of the size and complexity of the one that Hogwood proposed is organisation. His decision to arrange the contents by key is as good a solution as any, reflecting both contemporary practice found in, for example, *US-NYp*, Drexel

Figure 2. Arrangements of an air from *Bonduca* (Z.574/6). A: *GB-En*, Inglis 94/MS 3343; B: *US-Wc*, M21 M185 Case; C: *US-NH*, Filmer MS 24.

MS 3976 ('The Rare Theatrical') and the approach taken to keyboard music in many volumes of *Musica Britannica* (for example, volumes 27 and 28 containing Byrd's music). Furthermore, organisation by key has the advantage of encouraging the user to create their own suites of pieces following the practice of seventeenth-century players who were accustomed to making groupings for themselves (Woolley, 2018, pp. xv–xvi, xviii; Woolley et al., 2021, p. xix). However, it does mean that sequences of pieces by Purcell as they occur in individual sources become hidden from view. For example, c5,⁵ an arrangement of a hornpipe from *Bonduca* contained in *GB-En*, Inglis 94/MS 3343, continues with two G minor pieces, g14 and g15, from the same parent-work. The inclusion of this sort of information in the critical commentary is arguably of limited use since it would be difficult to reconstruct the order in which items occur. In this case, the settings in *GB-En*, Inglis 94/MS 3343 followed the order

in which the same movements appear in *Ayres for the Theatre*. The fact that this sequence is of music from the same theatrical work illustrates how arrangements could alternatively have been grouped by stage work. Often, sources do not provide information about the origins of a piece, preferring a more neutral title; perhaps music of the stage was well enough known for this information to be omitted or was not considered relevant for most players. In a printed volume, tables could be used to convey information about other possible ways in which the music could be ordered in performance. However, one advantage of a digital edition would be the possibility of grouping material in many different ways according to user need at the click of a mouse.

4. Variant versions and performance practice

In her 2013 book on *Musical Creativity in Restoration England*, Rebecca Herissone developed the concept of keyboard variants (Herissone, 2013a, pp. 345–346,

⁵ The provisional system of numbering items used by Hogwood in the edition as he left it has been retained. 'c5' refers to the fifth piece in C minor.

356–358, 367–374; Woolley et al., 2021, pp. xx–xxi), an idea drawing upon the concept of background variants developed by Alan Howard to explain variation between sources of concerted vocal music (Herissone, 2013a, pp. 245–259; Howard, 2012, pp. 99–101). Essentially notational in character, these variants affect only the surface detail of the music rather than its inherent harmonic or melodic substance. They arose because keyboard players tended to improvise by elaborating a treble–bass framework, often drawn from pre-existing music, as the repertory of arrangements shows. Variant versions of Purcell’s suite movements may likewise reflect elaborations by scribes who, as players, understood the music’s structural essence and sought to bring to bear on the notation their expectations for how the music should sound in performance.

As is implied above with respect to the *Fairy Queen* hornpipe, one issue that a critical edition of Purcell’s keyboard music needs to address is the existence of variant versions of the same piece or arrangement. As might be expected, there is not as much variance between the sources of some of the suites because their scribes had access to the printed versions. However, there are differences between sources and, perhaps encouraged by Dart, Ferguson published variants of Purcell’s Suite in G major in parallel in his 1964 edition along the lines shown in Figure 3. Hogwood, like Ferguson, observed that these variants offer information about performance practice – notably, in this case, unequal performance of paired quavers or semiquavers suggested by the dotted notation in one source but not the other. So, in presenting different versions in parallel in an edition, the performer can apply information about performance in a secondary source when interpreting the primary text. However, to judge from the draft materials he bequeathed to us, Hogwood was generally opposed to printing variants in parallel and also sought to limit the use of *ossia* staves to illustrate variation between sources on a single page, especially in suite movements. It may seem a minor point, but in fact relates to Hogwood’s views about how textual variation between sources is to be understood at a fundamental level, which are somewhat at odds with more recent research on notation and ontology in Restoration music.

In a print edition, the disadvantage of parallel texts is the increase in the number of page-turns in performance. There are three other alternatives to displaying the texts in parallel. The first is to create an edition which conflates the texts and provides a justification in the textual commentary along with a record of how the text has been arrived at. The second is to include *ossia* staves. The third, favoured by Hogwood, is to present each version as a separate piece. We are erring towards the conflation of texts where this seems appropriate and the use of *ossia*

staves where necessary, and when there is no reason to suppose that we are dealing with two distinct versions arising from authorial revision. In this regard we depart from Hogwood’s approach. However, any future digital edition could offer the opportunity to display variants in a number of different ways. It would be possible to display variant versions in parallel, as in the Ferguson example above, or to allow the user to double-click on bars to bring up source transcriptions or, using a IIIF manifest, digitised images of sources for the selected passage. The use of colour to highlight where there is variance between texts could act as an aid to the user, especially if different colours were used to signify particular categories of alteration. Such an edition could also allow the user to select from a number of options when downloading a piece for performance.

Hogwood was quite clear about how variant versions should be treated in a critical edition, observing that ‘there should be no amalgamation [of variants]; the present state of published virginalists’ music [i.e. in *Musica Britannica*] demonstrates the ease with which editors can create mongrels’ (Hogwood, 2003b, p. 85). His target was the first method of creating an edition, although his comment also hints at his views about the performer’s relationship with the score. In preferring to present variants as separate pieces, which makes comparison difficult, he also sought to discourage players from creating their own ‘mongrels’ of sorts, namely by applying variants from across multiple sources to a performance (not only unequal performance of semiquavers in almands, but also a wider range of variants encompassed by the concept of keyboard variants).

Although the conflation of sources leads to a text which never existed, arguably a philological approach is as valid as any other given the lack of textual fixity in the original sources. It is worth noting that its employment in most of the *Musica Britannica* editions of music by the virginalists is not as anachronistic as it may at first appear, so we can, therefore, take issue with Hogwood’s comments above. The *Le Strange* manuscripts, especially *GB-Lbl*, Add. MSS 39550–4, contain consort music written on the recto of each leaf, leaving the facing verso free for scribes to score up alternative readings to see whether they work. Every single difference between *Le Strange*’s versions and those in manuscripts owned by his friends is noted in the music text, regardless of whether it affects how the music sounds. Indeed, the approach is far more rigorous than anything to be found today and the result is in effect a seventeenth-century collected edition (Smith, 2016, pp. xxiv–xxviii, 186–187).

A criticism of some editions that take a ‘best text’ approach is that they are often neither an edition of a composer’s music nor one of a source. In some cases,

The image displays a musical score for the piece 'Almand' from Suite in G (Z.662/2) by J.S. Bach. The score is presented in two systems, A and B. System A shows the first three measures, and System B shows the next three measures. The music is in G major and 4/4 time. The right hand features intricate sixteenth-note patterns, while the left hand provides a steady bass line. The score includes dynamic markings like 'p' and 'f', and articulation marks like 'acc' and 'trill'. The piece concludes with '[etc.]'.

Figure 3. 'Almand' from Suite in G (Z.662/2), as published in Ferguson (1964a).

what purports to be a source edition is in reality a transcription with corrections made by the editor as required but without resorting to other sources: the 2020 edition of Fitzwilliam Virginal Book by Jon Baxendale and Francis Knights falls into this category (hardly surprising given the immense scale of this source); indeed, its editors describe it as a 'pseudo-facsimile' (Baxendale & Knights, 2020, vol. 1, p. xxxi). Using contemporary evidence to edit a text where other sources exist is surely better than relying on our own modern judgement. Such an edition may be scholarly in the sense of including exemplary prefatory material, but is not a critical one. Furthermore, the shifting emphasis onto scribes and users of music manuscripts together with the admittance of arrangements into the edition makes it unclear how a 'best text' could ever be defined. Other than conflating sources,

the only alternative is to present each variant as a separate piece (which makes little sense in cases where a text reflects one or more aspects of performance practice), or to use the introduction, textual commentary and *ossia* staves to convey the variety of notational practice when writing down the same piece.

Many current digital projects, such as Polish Digital Scores (n.d.), seek to create scholarly source transcriptions with minimal editorial interference rather than producing critical editions in which concordant texts are considered. However, the digital realm has great potential to reconcile an approach that conflates sources with one that presents a 'best text', providing the best of both worlds. A composer-centred edition can take into account all sources, whilst simultaneously a digital platform can encompass editions of each source using

concordant texts as a means of making any necessary corrections and resolving ambiguities in notation. Both approaches have their uses, depending on whether a user is interested in downloading pieces by a particular composer or needs pieces from a particular source to perform. In terms of online study, a digital infrastructure can allow variation between texts to be shown in music notation rather than as algebraic-looking formulae in a critical commentary: for example, a coloured symbol in a composer-centred edition could be used to indicate that one or more sources contain something different and clicking on it would bring up the variant. This type of approach would make material contained in the textual commentary of a printed volume accessible more directly from the score. Alternatively, it is possible to display versions from several sources in parallel, or to use linked data to connect each bar with its location on the digitised page of the original source, using a IIIF manifest (International Image Interoperability Framework, n.d.).

The state in which Hogwood left his edition, which envisaged including up to four different versions of some pieces presented consecutively rather than in parallel, clearly shows his rejection of a method based even on the modest amalgamation of variant texts. Similar ideas were expressed in his last essay on the urtext concept published in *Early Music* in 2013. Observing that ‘some composers were happy to allow multiple variants of their works into circulation’, he referred to some principles formulated by the Schubert scholar David Montgomery for how variant versions should be treated in a critical edition, namely, ‘do not mix versions’ and ‘do not assume that Schubert preferred one version over the other, chronology notwithstanding’ (Hogwood, 2013, p. 124). Interestingly, this sense of wanting to include variants as separate pieces within an edition mirrors the encoding of all sources needed for a digital edition. However, in the context of a printed edition of Restoration keyboard music, Hogwood’s preferred approach ironically tends to confer on each version a misleading sense of fixity which discourages comparison and hides degrees of variance since the versions do not appear alongside one another on the same pages. A digital edition could facilitate comparison between versions, potentially enabling players to recreate the sort of improvisatory performance conditions under which this and much other historical keyboard music was composed. This can be achieved only if a degree of equivalence and interchangeability between variants is considered valid.

Hogwood’s understanding of variants as a reflection of the ever-changing conceptions of the composer is widely held by editors of early keyboard music; for example, it informs the approach taken in the Urtext complete-works editions of composers such as Froberger edited

by Siegbert Rampe (Rampe, 2008, p. xxviii). Yet there are some clear problems with seeing textual differences as reflecting changing authorial conceptions, especially for the repertoire under consideration here. The concept of keyboard variants in Restoration keyboard music emphasises the role of scribes in shaping its notated manifestations. The crucial point is that, in whatever type of source they happen to survive – a contemporary print, an autograph or manuscript written by someone other than the composer – variants do not necessarily represent ways of performing it that have been fixed by the composer. Seventeenth-century notation may instead be thought of as expressing two domains: one consists of the composer’s intentions, which encompass the musical features of a piece that give it its essential identity, the other of performance practice. This means that the question for the editor becomes not one of ensuring that the player is able to reproduce each ‘version’, nor of disentangling what Purcell wrote from the accretions of others, but of how to present variants understood as information about the ways in which the music was played.

The situation is somewhat different when considering the sorts of arrangements considered above, since in these a scribe may, for example, preserve a melodic line (having perhaps absorbed a tune aurally and kept it in memory for future pedagogical use) whilst composing an entirely new bass. A draft of Hogwood’s textual commentary of No. D11 of the Purcell Society edition, inherited by the authors, states that ‘the bass line rarely follows the original’, but the user of the edition would have had to take his word for it since the projected printed volume lacks space to include versions for other performing resources. Although there are editions of keyboard music that include the original music used in arrangements (such as Smith, 1999), with a composer as prolific as Purcell, and whose music was popular enough to have been set many times by musicians other than himself, this is not normally possible in printed format. However, digital editions are different: they are not limited in the same way in terms of space. Encoding music of all sources of a piece, including those that would not ordinarily be considered for inclusion in a collected edition, would take Hogwood’s desire for an inclusive approach to a new level. It would allow not only a comparison to be made between a keyboard setting and its model, but also facilitate the computational study of arranging in the period. Ultimately, as datasets from multiple editions are combined, the digital domain will permit research questions to cross genres and span national and chronological boundaries.

In Figure 4, the arrangement of a ‘Trumpet Tune’ from Act IV of *Dioclesian* (Z.637/21) in *GB-Lbl*, Add. MS

Figure 4. Opening strain of ‘Trumpet Tune’ from Act IV of *Dioclesian* (Z.637/21) in two arrangements with the published string bass line. A: *GB-Lbl*, Add. MS 22099; B: Henry Purcell, *A Choice Collection*, 3rd edition (1699); C: Henry Purcell, *The Vocal and Instrumental Musick of the Prophetess or the History of Dioclesian* (London: J. Heptinstall for Henry Purcell, 1691).

22099 preserves the key and the melodic line, which differs in details of rhythm from a version connected with Purcell much in the same way as was seen in the previous example from the G-major suite (Figure 3). However, the bass line bears scant resemblance to the arrangement contained in the third edition of *A Choice Collection* where it is transposed; it is more commonly found in this key, perhaps to serve the needs of young players in avoiding the raised notes on the keyboard. The melodic line has many more ornaments and there are the vestiges of the second trumpet part in bar 3. There is some commonality between this and the published instrumental version, but they are not entirely consistent. It is possible to see all arrangements as belonging to the second domain, since not even bass lines are necessarily kept, a reflection of the way instrumental pieces often circulated as melodies in the Restoration period, either notated or memorised (Woolley, 2020). The seventeenth century saw a gradual shift from an aural and oral culture in which memory played a significant role to a predominantly literary one (Love, 2002, pp. 102–103). In music, the former continued to play a role: music was not seen as being primarily textual, so in the domestic sphere an arrangement could be made by ear of a tune heard once, potentially incorporating elements of performance practice from a specific occasion. Mary Chan (2002) gives an example of such an occasion, where John Hilton notated a live performance, stating that ‘the treble I tooke & prickt as mr Thorpe sung it’ (p. 131).

4.1. Notation of performance practice: touch

As well as conveying the possibility of *notes inégales* through the use of dotted rhythms in place of even note values, as observed above in relation to the Almand of the G-major suite (Figure 3), some sources provide evidence for the sort of touch that harpsichordists used at this period by notating more precisely how notes would have been played in performance. In Figure 5, the scribe of *GB-En*, Inglis 94/MS 3343 (A) notates each note in the left hand to be held into the next one within the bar, which of course does not reflect how the string bass part would have sounded in performance. In bar 4, the instrumental string bass line is followed in *GB-CDu*, 442/39j (B), although there are hints of overlapping notes in bar 5. The independent setting in *GB-Ldc*, MS 92b is also shown for the sake of completeness, but this is an eighteenth-century arrangement by John Reading (c.1685–1764): ‘Mr Hen. Purcell’s Hornpipe | Sett in to a Lesson by John. Reading’.

Arrangements for keyboard of Purcell’s grounds provide a fascinating glimpse into the variety of keyboard touch that is appropriate for this music as performers wrote down an approximation of what the music should sound like and how it should be played rather than taking a purely textual approach to the music (see also Herissonne, 2013a, pp. 375–377). An arrangement of ‘Here the deities approve’ from *Welcome to all the pleasures* is recognisably the same piece in all its sources,

Figure 5. 'Hornpipe' from *Bonduca* (Z.574/5). A: GB-En, Inglis 94/MS 3343; B: GB-CDu, 442/39j; C: GB-Ldc, MS 92b. D: Bass line from instrumental version.

but in matters of notational detail there are many differences in the way the music is notated (Figure 6). The way Purcell himself (presumably) presents the first bar in *The Second Part of Musick's Hand-maid* (source A in Figure 6) suggests a manner of performance where notes are overlapped wherever possible; in the other sources, the notation is much simpler. In these sources the notation operates a little like lute tablature, where the beginning of a note is given but the rhythm signs do not provide a precise duration. The holding over of notes in the bass line to create an inner part in bars 4–6 is a matter of keyboard performance practice since it would not have been possible to play the original bass line in this way. Of course, there is no immediate way of knowing whether scribes have simplified the texture as they found it in *The Second Part of Musick's Hand-maid*, or whether their unaltered version of the left-hand reflects a manuscript tradition and Purcell took it

upon himself to convey keyboard touch more precisely in the print.

The right-hand of the third bar is interesting in the same respect, too. The notation in the three other sources in Figure 6 is simpler than that found in *Musick's Hand-maid*. In the latter, the music is written such that notes in the right-hand overlap for the duration of a beat. The other three sources give no clue that the first note sounding on the first and second crotchets of the bar should be held, yet there is no rest to prevent the second note of the bar (a *b*) from sounding into the following crotchet unit. Purcell's notation is quite precise: notes in this bar should be held over, but with an articulation between the first two crotchet beats. The three sources which have the simpler accompaniment present variant readings of the melodic line (bars 4–7 of Example 8) with differences in the choice and placement of ornament signs, the inclusion of ornaments written out in notation, and the

The figure displays four different keyboard settings (A, B, C, D) of the piece 'A New Ground: Here the deities approve' from the opera *Welcome to all the pleasures* (Z.339/3). Each setting is presented as a grand staff with a treble and bass clef. System A shows the original manuscript with various ornaments and fingerings. System B shows a GB-CDp version with simplified ornaments. System C shows a GB-Lbl version with simplified ornaments. System D shows a GB-Lbl version with MS additions, including a 5-fingered ornament in the treble and a 7-fingered ornament in the bass.

Figure 6. Keyboard settings of 'A New Ground: Here the deities approve' from *Welcome to all the pleasures* (Z.339/3). A: *The Second Part of Musick's Hand-maid* (1689); B: GB-CDp, MS M.C.1. 39 (j); C: GB-Lbl, Add. MS 41205; D: GB-Lbl, Music Room Hirsch III, 472 [MS additions].

notation of dotted rhythms. It is difficult to know whether the right-hand at the opening of this piece reflects a broken style used for contemporary continuo practice, and the extent to which keyboard ornamentation reflected vocal practice.

The Ground ‘With him he brings the partner’ from *Ye Tuneful Muses* (Z.344/11) has a ‘walking’ ground bass similar to that of ‘Here the deities approve’. There is sufficient compositional consistency between sources containing the piece as it is set for keyboard to make it likely that it is one arrangement in many variant versions, reflecting a rich manuscript tradition. The opening bars illustrate how the notation of the *style brisé* texture of the right hand varies greatly between them, and – more importantly – demonstrates how this reflects diversity of performance practice between players/scribes. The point is best observed by noting where the rests come. In the first bar of Figure 7, source A implies an articulation at every quaver; source B holds over some notes to create a break after each crotchet unit, which is matched by the beaming of the bass in paired quavers; and sources C and E have rests that divide the bar into two minims. In bars 2–3, sources B, D and F notate notes in the right-hand overlapping one another in the same manner as was seen in Figure 6. It is likely that this reflects the style and technique of the period, and that performances of the piece as it occurs in sources such as A and E would have resulted in a similar sounding effect. Thus, the variety of notational practice for a piece such as this may be taken to have implications for other pieces where the surviving texts have the simpler-looking texture: an edition capable of presenting such information in an accessible way begins to give performers licence to apply what they learn from sources of one piece in other contexts. The right-hand rests in sources A and E provide a clear sense of articulation at the crotchet; sources C and F prefer division at the minim so it may therefore be that the lack of a tie between the E-flats in the alto of bar 3 between the first and second minim beats is not an oversight but entirely deliberate. Sources B and D are less consistent in the way the music in these two bars is phrased.

It would be difficult to justify presenting each variant as a separate item in a print edition when we are clearly dealing with variation between texts of the same arrangement, so the solution is likely to involve a degree of conflation of the kind Hogwood dismissed, together with an indication of how and why the sources differ conveyed through the introductory material and critical commentary. A digital edition, on the other hand, might allow the user on screen to view each of the variant versions and gain a greater understanding of contemporaneous keyboard performance practice.

5. Variants in the suite in A minor (Z.663)

Much of the textual variation that has been discussed thus far has been shown to reflect performance practice, information we argue should be made available to the player in a form that facilitates comparisons (e.g. by using *ossias*). Furthermore, we have demonstrated that variation is found as much among the repertory of arrangements as it is among Purcell’s suites that were conceived for keyboard and that even if the degrees of difference between sources may sometimes be considerably greater in the former, both reflect Herissone’s concept of keyboard variants. In a few cases, however, there is evidence of authorial revision which extends beyond the differences of surface detail that have been addressed so far. We argue that whenever such genuine compositional revision can be detected, treatment of the variant versions as separate pieces is justified.

A complicated case of variant versions where these considerations come to bear concerns the sources of the A minor suite, Z.663. To judge from the draft of his critical commentary, Hogwood planned to print four versions consecutively: the one in the British Library autograph (*GB-Lbl*, MS Mus. 1); the version in Purcell’s posthumous *A Choice Collection of Lessons*; one from *GB-Och*, Mus. 1177, copied by the Oxford professor Richard Goodson senior; and another in a manuscript copied by an anonymous scribe around 1700, *F-Pn*, rés 1186 bis. However, comparison of the sources reveals that there are really only two versions. The version in the autograph is essentially the same as that in *A Choice Collection of Lessons* and the Paris manuscript; all the differences are limited to keyboard variants. Thus, although the version in *A Choice Collection of Lessons* has served as the basis for most previous editions and recordings, it mostly combines readings found in the autograph and the Paris manuscript. It makes sense therefore to use the Paris version to show the fullest range of performance and notational variants in the sources while taking *GB-Lbl*, MS Mus. 1 as the base text. As in similar cases already discussed in this article, in the Purcell Society’s edition, we plan to show the variants in the Paris manuscript on *ossias* to enable comparison (Figure 8).

The Goodson version in *GB-Och*, Mus. 1177 likewise differs from the other sources (Figure 9). However, in this case some variants could also reflect an early version and, if so, it merits treatment in our edition as a separate piece. At some point after making his copies of the Almand and Corant, Goodson accessed the Z.663 Saraband, which he copied on available space later in his manuscript from *A Choice Collection of Lessons* (or a closely related source), writing above it: ‘Saraband to the lessons before, in A’.

Figure 7. Keyboard arrangement of Ground 'With him he brings the partner' from *Ye Tuneful Muses* (Z.344/11). A: GB-Cfm, Music MS 653; B: GB-Och, Mus. 1177; C: GB-Ob, MS Mus. Sch. E.397; GB-Lbl, Add. MS 47846; D: GB-Lbl, Add. MS 47846; E: GB-Lbl, Add. MS 31467 (ascribed 'Dr: Crofts. '); F: US-LAuc, M678 M4 H295 1710.

At the same time, he apparently modified his copy of the Almand to conform to some of the readings in the new source to which he now had access. In the final bar (b.17), the low A and a preceding rest in the LH part have been smudged out, partly in conformity with the reading in the autograph and *A Choice Collection*. Similarly, in b. 15, where some of the bass line was copied a third too low, Goodson changed it to conform to the version in the print. This second correction may simply reflect a copying error (it was common to write notes on the wrong line or space), but in any case, Goodson apparently

understood the versions of the Almand as distinct, seeing one as superseding the other. It is worth noting that alterations of this sort in English keyboard sources are rare and that they suggest Goodson's understanding of the compositional fabric extended to quite detailed and localised features. This does not undermine the validity of Herisson's concept of keyboard variants, although it suggests the extent to which some contemporaries placed a value on the precise form of the music's notation as is also implied by the *Le Strange* manuscripts mentioned above.

Figure 8. 'Almand' from Suite in A minor (Z.663/2). Main text: *GB-Lbl*, MS Mus. 1 (Purcell autograph); *D: F-Pn*, rés 1186 bis.

6. Digital directions?

Several of the music examples given above reflect the printed format of the new edition of Purcell's keyboard music: a main text is presented with an ossia where required, and other subsidiary sources are either to be given as separate items within the edition or considered in the textual commentary. Other examples contain parallel transcriptions of each source for a passage which

preserve as much graphical detail of the notation as possible. The former approach has great advantages: the performer has access to a scrupulously edited main text carried out by an expert in the field, with carefully curated alternative readings present as ossias. However, there is now a realisation that manuscripts do not contain so much texts of the music, but more a selection of different ways in which a piece may be realised in performance, recorded – however imperfectly – by the scribes

15

A:

B:

C:

D:

Figure 9. 'Almand' from Suite in A minor (Z.663/2), bars 15–17. A: *GB-Lbl*, MS Mus. 1 (with ornaments from *F-Pn*, rés 1186 in round brackets); B: *GB-Och*, Mus. 1177 (transcription); C: *GB-Och*, Mus. 1177 (facsimile); D: *A Choice Collection of Lessons for the Harpsichord or Spinnet Composed by ye late Mr. Henry Purcell*, 1696/9 (facsimile).

who played them (Smith, 2023, especially p. 152). The nineteenth-century model of a collected edition cannot hope to convey the array of performance possibilities present in the sources. This is particularly true for arrangements of music originally composed for other voices and instruments, which make up the vast majority of pieces associated with Purcell. Such considerations lead to a conception of the keyboard collected edition which is broader than one which seeks to establish a canon of music composed and arranged by the composer, jettisoning anything that appears on stylistic or source grounds to be the work of someone else. A volume of Purcell's collected keyboard pieces becomes one that embraces any of his music that is set for keyboard. The focus shifts from composer to the sources, and what they can tell us about keyboard practice in late seventeenth-century England. Through access to each source of a piece and every arrangement of a stage work, performers are immersed in all the possibilities afforded to them in terms of ornamentation, touch and *notes inégales*. A knowledge of performance practice gained through study of variant versions of one piece may lead to an understanding of how to approach another. Indeed, a study of the way in which performer-scribes arranged music in the seventeenth century could lead to new, stylistically appropriate arrangements of Purcell's music today: it is striking that keyboard arrangements draw upon only 14 of the 77 theatre works and odes composed by him, so there is plenty of scope for setting music from the rest; furthermore, an interesting research question might be to address why the pool of original material was so narrow.

Some approaches, such as the interactive edition of Albertus Bryne's keyboard music by Terence Charlston and Heather Windram (Charlston & Windram, 2008), supplement a printed edition with source material in digital form. Included with the printed book is a CD containing links to transcriptions, facsimiles and sound files. In addition, it provides webpages where the edition and the principal source can be browsed in synchronisation, although this no longer works in today's web browsers, pointing to an inherent weakness in digital platforms for editions that was one focus of the AHRC network, 'Digital Directions'. As Charlston and Windram explained in their printed edition of Bryne, 'by making the source material available and keeping the editorial intervention minimal and transparent, users can trace how the final Performing Edition has been achieved, and are able to use their own critical judgement to make independent editorial decisions' (Charlston & Windram, 2008, pp. v–vi). The online environment likewise enables the presentation of many more variants than is possible in a printed edition. Resources such as the Online

Chopin Variorum Edition are intended to encourage the user to explore a range of options in performance through engagement with variant versions of Chopin's music (Rink, 2021, pp. 57–59). However, it is worth pondering further what such editions can offer that a printed edition cannot, especially with respect to how performance variants can be presented in a way that all relevant information is brought to the user's attention. The question is largely one of design, particularly in terms of User Interface.

One useful tool when preparing an edition involves collating all the texts in parallel transcriptions along the lines of some examples in this article. Traditionally, the finished product then involves choices to be made about which text is to be preferred, and which others are relegated to an *ossia* or critical commentary. With repertoire such as Purcell's keyboard music (broadly conceived), this gives a distorted picture of the music and its performance. A digital edition would allow a multidimensional approach in which any or all of the primary sources can be edited as the prime text, with errors corrected by reference to other versions, which could be displayed to give the user a sense of other possibilities. Furthermore, linked data can create connections between a bar or system of the edition and the digitised image of its source. Corrections are much more easily made in the digital realm than to printed editions, and new evidence can be incorporated as it comes to light. The importance of metadata cannot, therefore, be overstated, and this includes keeping an accurate record of the version history for each piece and, indeed, for supplementary introductory material.

One model would enable the user to create their own editions by making choices about which variants to use. On the face of it, this democratisation of the editing process seems attractive. However, Hogwood perhaps had a point about 'mongrel' editions: there is a distinction to be drawn between a scholarly editor bringing supplementary sources to bear on editing a main text, and someone with limited knowledge of the source material making a patchwork out of bars drawn from multiple sources without any rationale. Arguably, for us there still needs to be a distinction between text and act: the inclusion of multiple variants in an online edition would be intended to draw the performer's attention to the wide array of possibilities in performance rather than to allow performance practice to be fossilised in versions made up from variants created at different times and in different contexts. However, in all likelihood they would need to be able to download a 'clean' text without parallel transcriptions for practical use, perhaps selecting from several pre-determined options. The digital edition has enormous potential for what can be included within it

and how it might be displayed, but there is still a role for the scholarly, expert editor.

6.1. Sustainability

Throughout this article, we have highlighted the ways in which a digital infrastructure for collected editions might be used to solve the issues that arise in relation to editing seventeenth-century keyboard music, the ways in which a digital edition would allow research questions to be interrogated through computational analysis of the data, and how a digital platform could be dynamic enough to allow users to customise the display and print of musical notation. The 'Digital Directions' project aimed to bring together scholars and editors of early music with music technologists, computer scientists, librarians, and board members representing three collected editions (*Musica Britannica*, *Early English Church Music* and *Purcell Society Edition*) to explore how such editions might exploit the digital domain. It quickly became apparent that recent technological developments in music, especially the creation of MEI as a relatively new standard for encoding texts of music and Verovio as a means of rendering code into notation, made possible all the digital possibilities identified in this article, and that the main challenges lay elsewhere.

When the Royal Musical Association set up the *Musica Britannica* Trust in 1952, it did not seek to publish its own series but went into partnership with Stainer & Bell. This helped to ensure that the printed series of volumes had the best chance of longevity, and that it benefited from the financial stability offered by the business model of a professional publisher. However, digital resources tend to be even more expensive than their physical counterparts to create, and often represent the outcome of a research project. Indeed, until now the focus of most digital music projects has been on musicological exploration of sources and their analysis rather than the creation of usable editions, and the visitor to their websites needs an advanced understanding of the material to begin using them.

Currently, there is no mechanism for the preservation of such resources: there is no one whose job it is to ensure that they remain functional beyond the end of a project. The AHRC aspires to create iDAH, a 'national infrastructure for digital innovation and curation' (*AHRC Strategic Delivery Plan 2022–2025*, p. 13), but its development is currently at a very early stage which makes it vital to consider how to preserve data and software tools. During 'Digital Directions', David Lewis proposed conceptualising layers of digital conservation: the encoded data is most likely to survive, and software tools that have become standard across several projects stand a reasonable chance of remaining functional. It is at the top

level where tools have been customised for a particular project that there is the greatest risk. Andrew Hankinson recommends keeping the data in as many formats as possible, including printouts of the music.

The sustainability of a digital edition is therefore in no small measure dependent upon an ability to maintain its platform. Although national institutions such as the British Library are exploring how digital resources may be preserved as well as printed ones (as reported by Rupert Ridgewell during 'Digital Directions'), currently it is incumbent upon those creating digital music editions to make provision for their long-term sustainability in terms of preservation of data and maintenance of software. This is inextricably linked to funding models.

All three collected editions rely on a subscription model inherited from the eighteenth and nineteenth centuries: whereas in earlier times subscribers would be wealthy individuals, in the twentieth century they were university and research libraries. This model is breaking down in the twenty-first century as university curricula expand and there are thus many more calls upon shrinking library budgets. Also, in many ways the subscription model is problematic in an age where the impact of research is increasingly important. Little attention is paid to the users of collected editions, which may be consulted in research libraries by those in reach of one but often cannot be borrowed, rendering them of limited use to performers unlikely to be able to afford their own copy. Most users are likely to need only one or two items of keyboard music from a volume rather than the whole book. Stainer & Bell offers an offprint service for pieces in *Musica Britannica*, and doubtless will do so for the keyboard volume of the *Purcell Edition*, but individual items within these national collections remain hidden from view in Google searches, making it difficult for the casual user to know that these scholarly, critical editions exist. Metadata in an encoded digital edition would make each piece far more visible in an online environment. Today's potential users of an edition such as this expect it to be online for instant download, making the move to a digital platform essential for wider accessibility. They also expect access to such music to be free of charge, often preferring to download a freely available, unreliable edition rather than the latest scholarly one. The implication is the need to persuade users of the intrinsic value of a critical edition and that it worth paying for it.

A collected edition will be sustainable financially only if it truly engages with communities of user, whether it remains in printed format, moves online or adopts a hybrid model. Many of the possible features presented during the course of this article will be of greatest benefit to the specialist musicologist or professional performer. However, the keyboard music of Purcell in particular is as

suiting to the needs of young learners as it is to the professional player because much of it was originally intended for them. Now is surely as good a time as any to be making critical editions such as this accessible to a much broader audience? The involvement of all three UK-based collected editions in the ‘Digital Directions’ makes it likely that they will be engaged with any future project. Such a project needs to involve a strong element of codesign, where users have a significant input into both features and User Interface. It is important not to assume that any feature identified as being useful by us will necessarily be a priority for a user. Similarly, it is important to recognise that different groups of users will have differing needs and that it may be necessary to think in terms of multiple interfaces to meet them. For example, a beginner pianist will need guidance on which pieces would be suitable for them but not necessarily the sort of source information and guidance on harpsichord performance practice that a professional or advanced amateur might require, or the musicologist’s need for access to data for computational analysis. Ultimately, a dynamic, digital collected edition of Purcell’s keyboard music will reply on engaging multiple communities of user in such a way that they are invested in the project.

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